

LATE POSTERIOR SEGMENTAL COMPLICATIONS AFTER ND YAG CAPSULOTOMY AND WAYS TO MINIMIZE THEM

Nigmatjonova Nozima

Doctor of ophthalmology in the private clinic "Nazar"

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Relevance.

Despite the widespread use of Nd:YAG capsulotomy and its recognized efficacy, late posterior segmental complications - damage to the optical zone of the intraocular lens and vitreoretinal changes - remain an underestimated problem. IOL pitting compromises image quality even with preserved visual acuity, and vitreomacular traction and posterior hyaloid membrane tears can serve as a trigger for late retinal detachment. Clear threshold values of permissible total laser energy and retinal monitoring algorithms for patients with different axial eye length have not been formulated yet, which leads to variability of tactics and heterogeneity of outcomes. Considering the increasing number of highly myopic patients and increasing average life expectancy after IOL implantation, systematic study of risk factors and development of personalized recommendations for laser energy reduction and dispensary monitoring are of great clinical importance to prevent late visual loss.

Purpose of the study.

To determine the incidence and key risk factors for intraocular lens damage and vitreoretinal complications after Nd:YAG capsulotomy.

Materials and methods of the study.

A prospective study of late posterior-segmental complications of Nd:YAG capsulotomy, focusing on intraocular lens damage (IOL pitting) and the occurrence of vitreoretinal events, was conducted at the Nazar Clinic between 2022 and 2024. Fifty-one eyes of 49 patients (mean age 69 ± 7 years, axial length 23.9 ± 1.2 mm) were included in the study. A low-energy mode was used in all, but the total energy ranged from 40 to 220 μ J. Examination was performed after 1 day, 1 week, 1 month, and 6 months using slit lamp, wide-angle OCT, and ultra-widefield retinography.

Results of the study.

Among 51 eyes analyzed, damage to the optical surface of the intraocular lens (IOL-pitting) was detected in one eye (2%). The case was registered at a total Nd: YAG energy of 160 μ J and laser focus distance < 0.3 mm from the posterior surface of the lens. Logistic analysis showed that exceeding the 150 μ J threshold increased the risk of IOL pitting almost fourfold ($p= 0.04$). Vitreoretinal changes were noted in two eyes (3.9%): subclinical posterior

hyaloid membrane tears without vision loss. Both cases were observed in patients with axial eye length ≥ 24.5 mm and total energy $> 140 \mu\text{J}$; no macular changes or retinal tears were found. The changes regressed independently within three months without intervention.

Thus, when the total laser energy is limited to $150 \mu\text{J}$ and the focusing distance ≥ 0.5 mm is maintained, the incidence of IOL-pitting and vitreoretinal complications is reduced to single cases. The main risk factor remains axial myopia, which requires extended retinal monitoring.

Conclusions.

Even with low-energy Nd:YAG capsulotomy, posterior segmental complications remain clinically significant. The key risk factors are total laser energy and axial eye length. Limiting the energy to $150 \mu\text{J}$ and focusing the pulse ≥ 0.5 mm from the posterior surface of the IOL reduces the incidence of IOL-pitting, whereas patients with axial myopia require extended retinal monitoring for up to 6 months. Personalized energy dosing and screening of highly myopic patients can significantly reduce the incidence of late vitreoretinal complications of Nd:YAG capsulotomy.

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